

PUBLIC INFRASTRUCTURES

RESULTS OF A SURVEY AMONG LERU MEMBERS

REPORT OF THE PUBLIC INFRASTRUCTURE TASK FORCE, A WORKING GROUP UNDER AUSPICES OF LERU'S OPEN SCIENCE AMBASSADORS, SUPPORTED BY MAURITS VAN DER GRAAF (PLEIADE MANAGEMENT & CONSULTANCY), JULY 2023

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ABOUT THE REPORT

This report gives the results of a survey among LERU members ([League of European Research Universities](#)), conducted by the Public Infrastructure Taskforce, a working group under auspices of LERU's Open Science Ambassadors. Members of the Public Infrastructure Taskforce (in alphabetical order): Etienne Augé (Paris-Saclay), Paul Ayris, (co-chair, UCL), Anne-Catherine Fritzinger (Sorbonne), Paola Galimberti (Milan), John Renner Hansen (Copenhagen), Kristoffer Holmqvist (Lund), Ignasi Labastida (Barcelona), Andrea Malits (Zürich), Christian Oesterheld (Zurich), Frans Oort, (co-chair, Amsterdam), Lars Pastewka (Freiburg), Jeroen Sondervan (Utrecht), Kimmo Tuominen (Helsinki), Demmy Verbeke (Leuven), Immo Warntjes (Dublin), Saskia Woutersen (Leiden). The work was supported by Pascal Braak (Amsterdam), Robert van der Vooren (Amsterdam), and Maurits van der Graaf (Pleiade Management & Consultancy). The survey was developed and distributed to the LERU members by the Taskforce. Maurits van der Graaf was commissioned to write this report, which has been published with DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8209067.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 REPORTING THE SURVEY RESULTS

LERU's Public Infrastructure Taskforce (PIT) has composed a questionnaire on public infrastructures for publishing research output. This survey has been distributed among all 22 LERU universities in the period August – November 2022.

This report describes the results of the filled-in questionnaires that were received from 16 universities. The setup of the report follows closely the setup of the questionnaire:

- The questionnaire consisted of six sections; these sections are presented in the report as separate chapters.
- The texts in the survey are presented throughout the report in italics, the questions in bold.
- Some questions enabled a quantification of the results which is presented in tables.
- For other questions, the responses by the respondents were summarised as much as possible and/or by presenting a few typical responses.
- Factual information provided by the respondents is presented with the University name involved. Opinions and comments by respondents are presented anonymously.
- Some respondents did not fill out all sections. Therefore, per section a table is presented with an overview of the responding universities. In addition, when a section was filled-in, sometimes not all questions were answered, or a respondent referred to another answer. For readability reasons, this is not reported.

Based on this report, the PIT has given its observations and recommendations in a separate document.¹

1.2 INTRODUCTORY TEXT TO THE SURVEY

LERU's Public Infrastructure Taskforce (PIT) is exploring what universities can do in establishing a public infrastructure to publish all kinds of academic output – in all stages of the research process – in open access, while preserving digital sovereignty, academic quality, and integrity.²

The PIT is investigating if and how universities can be provided with and involved in such an infrastructure. To this end, we are conducting a survey among LERU members to gather good practices, to get an idea of what kind of infrastructure is already in place in the respective countries of LERU members, and to what extent existing infrastructures meet the needs and wishes of the academic community. Aspects around quality control, costs, long-term access, and responsible metrics will be addressed.

Digital sovereignty

The term 'digital sovereignty' is widely used and there are a variety of definitions. The World Economic Forum uses the definition³: "Digital sovereignty refers to the ability to have control over your own digital destiny – the data, hardware and software that you rely on and create."

Digital sovereignty is of utmost importance for universities and other academic institutions as one of the preconditions for equitable and open research and teaching. Increasing prices for reading and publishing charged by publishers as well as far-reaching developments towards oligopolistic structures

¹ On the need to establish public infrastructure to preserve digital sovereignty. Two-page summary of the results of LERU's Public Infrastructure Task Force (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8209173](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8209173)).

² For the PIT charter see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7028253>

³ <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/03/europe-digital-sovereignty/>

of these companies are exerting pressure on universities' budgets, independence, and control. As a result, in recent years, more and more universities have no longer been able to provide all the relevant literature necessary for research and teaching, nor to support their researchers fully in open access publishing. Even more worryingly, a new data business has emerged in the field of scholarly communication, based on academics' citations and downloads provided by big publishers and related data companies focusing on bibliometrics and citation indexes. These approaches mine researchers' and students' handling of data, analyse these data, and process them into 'scholarly productivity impact' assessments and predictions of future research trends. As a result, they can influence the academic reward system and evaluative decision-making systems.⁴

LERU's PIT therefore envisions an open and public infrastructure landscape which is not dominated by publishers and data companies, but one which will embrace digital sovereignty and be characterised as follows:

- 1) The infrastructure landscape is not-for-profit and led and controlled by the academic community. Appropriate governance and oversight are secured.
- 2) Funding is secured by the public sector, i.e., universities and funders. Authors do not have to pay to publish, and readers do not have to pay to get access.
- 3) Establishing, sustaining, and operating the infrastructure is ensured by cooperative work models.
- 4) Different research cultures to generate and release knowledge in their respective disciplines are recognized and respected. Differences in terms of publication outputs, quality standards and metrics are to be reflected and included.
- 5) If partnerships with commercial providers are considered to be necessary, a balance of interests must be ensured.
- 6) Hardware and software components are as open as possible and as closed as needed (e.g., when it comes to storing personal data).
- 7) Bibliometric indicators and metrics about the impact of authors, journals and other research outputs are responsible and preferably generated by the communities themselves.
- 8) Standards such as COPE, the Committee for Publication Ethics, best practice of open licences as well as technical standards such as Persistent Identifiers are to be included and continuously to be evaluated.

This survey will investigate what it would take to retain digital sovereignty by setting up a high-quality (community owned and controlled) open access publication infrastructure. The survey has six sections: (A) governance and sustainability, (B) recognition and rewards, (C) quality assurance and control, (D) practical implementation, (E) copyright, licensing, and data protection, and (F) technical requirements.

⁴ Pooley, J., (2022) "Surveillance Publishing", *The Journal of Electronic Publishing* 25(1), <https://doi.org/10.3998/jep.1874>; Jansen, D., (19 October 2021) "Safeguarding academic and digital sovereignty: a model for action", *Expert Voices* (eua.eu), <https://eua.eu/resources/expert-voices/250:safeguarding-academic-and-digital-sovereignty-a-model-for-action.html>; Loridi, L. (2020) The Fight for Digital Sovereignty: What It Is, and Why It Matters, Especially for the EU. *Philosophy & Technology* (33), 369–378, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-020-00423-6>

2. GOVERNANCE AND SUSTAINABILITY

2.1 DIGITAL SOVEREIGNTY

The term 'digital sovereignty' is widely used and there are a variety of definitions. The World Economic Forum uses the definition⁵: "Digital sovereignty refers to the ability to have control over your own digital destiny – the data, hardware and software that you rely on and create."

LERU's PIT envisions an open infrastructure landscape which is not dominated by publishers and data companies but enables the digital sovereignty of universities and other academic institutions.

Q1: How does your university currently endorse digital sovereignty?

This survey question has been filled in by all but one participating universities.

Three universities stated that digital sovereignty is incorporated as a principle in their policies:

- The University of Freiburg has a [strategy paper](#) published with recommendations on conditions for agreements with third parties, open standards, a strict regulatory framework for the market and for joint buying power in the market. Also, the topic of digital sovereignty seems high on the agenda in the German higher education sector, as is shown by a [discussion paper](#) of the Alliance for Higher Education in Germany on this topic.
- The University of Amsterdam is also active on this topic: the former Rector Magnificus has started a discussion about the independence of science in the current digital age and has advocated for a European 'Digital University act' that would give a legal basis for the digital sovereignty of academia. There is also a roadmap for digital sovereignty drafted with various action lines such as (1) create awareness, inform, and educate; (2) make digital sovereignty as a guiding principle by procurement; (3) public infrastructures first; (4) develop infrastructure and define guiding principles and (5) lobbying for support of funders, for legislation and build consortiums.
- The Leiden University endorses digital sovereignty by creating awareness within the University. Digital sovereignty is also a principle in the data policy of the University: the University always remains the owner of its data and then storing data on supply assistance, the responsibility of the University's data has to be secured in the agreement in addition to data portability so that the data can be transferred to another supplier.

Lund University	Y
University of Freiburg	Y
Universiteit Leiden	Y
University of Amsterdam	Y
Utrecht University	Y
KU Leuven	Y
Sorbonne University	Y
University Paris-Saclay	Y
University of Strasbourg	Y
Université de Genève	N
University of Zurich	Y
University of Barcelona	Y
University of Helsinki	Y
Trinity College Dublin	Y
University of Milan	Y
University of Edinburgh	Y

A number of respondents have seen this issue in the light of open science, research data and/or publications and less so as a specific issue that is separately treated in University policies: some of the responding universities point to infrastructures (mostly regarding research data infrastructures, sometimes regarding Diamond OA publication platforms) they have developed or are using that are in public hands (6 universities). One University points to their requirements related to data management planning which includes a focus on the long-term reusability of any research output including issues of sovereignty, i.e., being able to reuse data, hardware and software in a way that is not restricted by third parties). Three universities point to their institutional open science policies. One respondent states that digital sovereignty is not explicitly endorsed. Another University admits that its actions

⁵ <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/03/europe-digital-sovereignty/>

regarding digital sovereignty are rather limited, while another states that digital sovereignty is not endorsed in any of their regulations or policies.

Q2 How can universities endorse digital sovereignty?

The answers can be categorised as follows:

- **Awareness, education, and guidelines:** many respondents mention awareness raising and education throughout the institution as well as providing guidelines
- **Institutional policies:** some respondents mention that digital sovereignty should be included in the institutional policies as a principle. One respondent adds 'actively engaging in the policy debate at a national and EU level on data related policies'.
- **Open source:** many respondents state that (the use of) open source infrastructures is one of the most important pillars of digital sovereignty.
- **Rights retention:** also, rights retention policies are seen as part of digital sovereignty by many respondents.
- **Research life-cycle supporting services:** one respondent states that support services throughout the research life-cycle are important: digital sovereignty can then be guaranteed by providing appropriate tools, applications, and platforms for each phase of the life-cycle of a research project.
- **Procurement:** one respondent focuses on the selection of systems and tools that are implemented within the University. Investment and support in mission-aligned and community-led infrastructures and tools should be prioritised over others. An important aspect is to allocate enough time to investigate the alternatives to commercial tools.

2.2 ORGANISATION AND TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

Many universities have their local - or networked - publication infrastructure with their own governance and business model, for example (data) repositories and publishing houses. Transition to a community owned and efficient public infrastructure raises questions about centralised governance, ownership, sustainability, and financing.

Q3. Does your university have infrastructures (e.g., repositories, publication platforms) for publications, journals, research data and other research outputs? Please state the type of technical infrastructure and the software.

Q4. If your university has infrastructures, who owns the infrastructures?

Q5. If your university has infrastructure(s), how are they governed?

Q6. If your university has infrastructure(s), who covers/covered the necessary pre-investment for designing, setting-up and launching these infrastructures?

Q7. If your university has infrastructure(s), who covers/covered the necessary pre-investment for designing, setting-up and launching these infrastructures?

Q8. If your university has infrastructure(s), what mechanisms are in place for long-term sustainability?

Lund University	Y
University of Freiburg	Y
Universiteit Leiden	Y
University of Amsterdam	Y
Utrecht University	Y
KU Leuven	Y
Sorbonne University	Y
University Paris-Saclay	Y
University of Strasbourg	Y
Université de Genève	Y
University of Zurich	Y
University of Barcelona	Y
University of Helsinki	Y
Trinity College Dublin	Y
University of Milan	Y
University of Edinburgh	Y

Most of these questions have been filled out by all respondents. However, the questions Q4 to Q7 are not always filled out consistently for all infrastructures mentioned in Q3. Q8 has been differently understood by the respondents: some have answered this in terms of financial sustainability, others in terms of long-term preservation. All answers have been summarized per University in table 1 in Appendix A. Here we sum up the main results:

- **Repository function:**
 - All universities have an institutional repository for self-archiving. Two French universities use a national repository (HAL) for this purpose. One University (Freiburg) has developed a platform that combines the repository function with the publication platform (see below).
 - Seven universities report to use a CRIS system, one 'with a repository for self-archiving connected. Five of those CRIS systems are commercially owned (3x Pure – Elsevier and 1x Converis – Clarivate), but the repositories 'behind the CRIS' usually are not. However, one respondent reports that Pure is also used as a publications repository. Of the two other CRIS systems, one is national and based on DSpace, one is in-house developed.
 - One University reports a separate repository for theses and other digital objects such as grey literature. This repository is using DSpace.
 - Regarding the repositories, one can conclude that the ownership of these repositories is in public hands, as is the governance.
- **Publication platform:**
 - 9 universities have implemented a publication platform for journals: 8 are using the OJS software for this, 1 is using the LODEL software. Three universities also report additionally the use of OMP for monograph publishing on the publication platform.

- One University has not a central publication platform but reports that several faculties publish journals on institutional servers.
- Ownership and governance are in public hands.
- **Research data infrastructures:**
 - Only one University (Lund) does not have an infrastructure for research data. Another university (Freiburg) is in the process of implementing multiple data publication platforms (InvenioRDM and OMERO are mentioned).
 - The other universities do have implemented infrastructures for storing and publishing research datasets:
 - The French universities use *recherche data gouv*, a recently developed national platform by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research.
 - Four universities use shared systems:
 - Two Dutch universities use DataverseNL, a system based on data versus software, shared with other institutions and managed by DANS (a national institution).
 - The two Swiss universities also make use of infrastructures that have been developed in partnership with other universities.
 - One University has two data repositories: an institutional open access data repository using DSpace and an institutional long-term data retention solution, using local hardware and self-developed software.
 - Finally, one University uses Figshare, a commercially owned infrastructure.
 - Ownership and governance appear to be in public hands at all but one participating university.

As stated earlier, the question about long-term sustainability has been interpreted differently:

- 6 universities have answered this question in terms of financial sustainability. One University sees a risk here for open science platforms: they are developed with time-limited project funds and are difficult to transition to permanent services.
- 9 have answered this question in terms of preservation of the data and the systems: the data from a number of systems are preserved by the national libraries or other long-term archives such as LOCKSS (see also chapter 5, Q24).

2.3 REGARDING LERU'S PIT EFFICIENT OPEN AND PUBLIC INFRASTRUCTURE

LERU's PIT therefore envisions an open and public infrastructure landscape which is not dominated by publishers and data companies, but one which will embrace digital sovereignty.

About this vision the following questions are asked:

Q9: At which level would an infrastructure best be organised (university, national, international), and why?

Q10. How would an infrastructure ideally be governed?

Q11. What would be an ideal ownership model for an infrastructure?

Q12. What would be an ideal financing model for an infrastructure?

14 universities answered a number of these questions. The responses can be summarised as follows:

- Two respondents stated that they found it difficult to answer these questions as the infrastructure itself was not defined enough in their eyes. Others answer in a similar fashion with replies like 'depending on the needs'.
- One respondent has also seen failures in similarly organised platforms:
 - Infrastructure should be organised at all levels. This takes account of a combination of localised complexities with economies of scale and the requirements for infrastructure, particularly for research data, to be close to the instrumentation producing it; it will be important to have complementarity and mutual discoverability between the layers. National infrastructure in Ireland has a mixed record of success with several national initiatives discontinued despite their success and promise, e.g., Expertise Ireland (the all-island research portal, 2001-2009), Rian.ie (Ireland's open access research portal, 2011-2021), the NDLR (Ireland's national digital learning repository, c.2013-2017). All were fully functioning components of publicly-funded national infrastructure that failed to receive sustained support at institutional and government levels.
- There is a reluctance among many respondents for international platforms. A few answers in full:
 - Due to the different funding and financing streams (also regarding involved funding agencies) as well as due to different legal frameworks, it seems to be very difficult to organise it on an international level.
 - Many universities have their local or networked publication infrastructures with their own governance and business model. Transition to a community owned efficient public infrastructure raises questions about governance, ownership, sustainability, and financing.
 - We think the national level is the most realistic and desirable level for organising research infrastructures in general.
 - We believe that infrastructures should be organised by communities and that some form of competitive coexistence of different solutions improve service quality. Infrastructure organised on purely international levels typically inhibits this type of competition. Infrastructure in terms of a base level the generic surface is hence the best organised on the University level. The individual researchers of fields can then deploy the solutions/services on top of this basic infrastructure.
- However, a number of respondents do suggest possible setups for international infrastructures:
 - Given the nature of scholarly communication, infrastructure on the international level would be the obvious choice. More realistically, the public infrastructure would also take

Lund University	Y
University of Freiburg	Y
Universiteit Leiden	Y
University of Amsterdam	Y
Utrecht University	Y
KU Leuven	Y
Sorbonne University	Y
University Paris-Saclay	Y
University of Strasbourg	Y
Université de Genève	N
University of Zurich	Y
University of Barcelona	Y
University of Helsinki	Y
Trinity College Dublin	Y
University of Milan	Y
University of Edinburgh	N

the form of an alliance between existing mission-aligned platforms and tools. Examples are: OJS, open citations, open knowledge maps.

- A thematic infrastructure would probably be best organised at the European level in association with a strict relation of the research community at the European level. It might interconnect national infrastructures, themselves interconnecting University infrastructures. An example is elixier-europe.org.
- Some research areas would definitely benefit from a more international infrastructure. EOSC is one example of such an infrastructure that we are very much support, although we also see that coordinating and setting up an infrastructure at that scale takes a lot of time and effort. National coordination is probably a requisite for any future international infrastructure.
- Ideally, the infrastructure would be a distributed system, built on University repositories, owned, and controlled by universities, consolidated in a joint system, governed by all participating universities jointly. Ideally, this joint system would be a global system, but as financing is mostly nationally organised, as are laws and regulations, the idea of a distributed system might be repeated.
- Internationally should be preferred as there are already so many systems on an international level and science is mostly done in an international field. The advantage of an infrastructure on the University level is that it is easy to control, but maintenance can be complex and costly. National might combine the two disadvantages of the University level and the international level: less control and too small for science on an international level. It would be interesting and more efficient to set up an infrastructure in a consortium model instead of a repository at every University. Japan has such consortium infrastructure.
- Internationally, EOSC and OpenAIRE are offering promising services. The OpenAIRE Researcher Community Dashboard has been recommended by Trinity College Dublin to European university networks with Irish partners.
- For some infrastructures it is strategically more efficient to do this as a collective (national or international).

Summarising, many respondents see a three- or two-level federative model as the most feasible option: an institutional level and/or a national level and then the international level that interconnects the national and/or institutional infrastructures with one respondent pleading for a consortium model. The questions about governance, ownership and financing are answered in a similar vein. A few typical answers:

Regarding governance:

- Local repositories should of course be governed by the individual universities, leaving room for their own choices in quality assurance et cetera. The higher levels of governance for the consolidated repository or network of repositories might have governance similar to the EOSC governance.
- Probably by a mixed board of people who represent the financial as well as the academic and operational responsibilities.
- Depends on the scope of the infrastructure. If it is national, all partners should be represented. If it is at the University level, all stakeholders should be invited to be part of the governing body that ideally should be led by the unit, service, or vice rectorate in charge.
- Community driven.
- The infrastructure should be governed/steered by the researchers who use it. Setting up an infrastructure implies setting up of corresponding governance structures.
- Individual stakeholders need to take responsibility for the layers they provide, but there also needs to be a stakeholder forum to ensure interoperability. At university level, infrastructure would ideally

be governed by a group of senior representatives with decision making power and budget allocation to focus on the needs of the research community.

- Ideally be an open and transparent governance model.

Regarding ownership:

- Universities own their own repositories, the joint infrastructure would be owned by the joint universities
- The ownership issue is part of the governance model. With regard to content, ownership should remain with the researchers.
- Owned by the University or by the community that uses it.
- The DOAJ model is suggested.
- Many infrastructures are offered with a steering committee and a user community.
- The model developed in the HPC (principle of third parties) adapts well to the mode of operation in the University. A part of it is owned by each University and the parties shared in research infrastructures.
- The universities should at least be the owner of the content of the infrastructure. Under strict conditions, it is not necessary to be the owner of the infrastructure if the University only makes use of an infrastructure. One of the conditions should be that the data should not be used by an external party, and that it should be easy to transfer the data to another infrastructure. Digital sovereignty must be safeguarded.
- The base level infrastructure like general storage capacities, computational resources and networks should be (centrally) owned and run by the University IT providers. For larger demands, the cost model makes it desirable to balance demands between the different user groups/scientific communities.
- Infrastructure should be owned by the university and funded by the university through various mechanisms. National and international infrastructure should be owned by state bodies with strong representation from academia, industry, and society.
- Ownership should ideally be secured within academia, in a collective of universities/funders and/or scholarly-led organisations.

Regarding financing:

- Material costs can either be distributed across participating universities or paid for by the national government. Personal and time can be provided by universities as in-kind contributions.
- Costs should be covered by national HE organisations/funders, not by individual researchers.
- If it is at the University level, the University should analyse how to cover the costs. If it is national, all the parties should cover some part.
- The most ideal model could be a consortium model, which also has the possibility of free choice of each infrastructure to support. JISC for example supports different repositories (DSpace, Eprints, Islandorica).
- Central funding, international, and national or at the University level.
- Ideally the infrastructure would receive continued funds through a governing body at the EU, national or state level. An alternative financing model (although less preferred) would be contributions from member institutions. arXiv is an example of such a model. Finally (least preferred), paper publication models currently used by for-profit publishers could certainly also be implemented to support an open infrastructure.
- Infrastructure is a requirement as part of doing research. It should be funded by the state. New implementations and major upgrades should be possible through infrastructure development funds, whereas smaller maintenance allocations should be a part of the block grant.
- Support and donation model (see the Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services model).

3. RECOGNITION AND REWARDS

3.1 FRAMEWORKS AND METRICS

Principles expressed in statements such as DORA, the Leiden Manifesto and the Hong Kong principles urges universities, funders, and other parties to improve the ways in which the output of scientific research is evaluated.

Instead of counting articles and relying on metrics such as the Journal Impact Factor, research success should be assessed on its own merit (on article- or output-level) and through its optimal output form. The platform envisioned by LERU's PIT should highlight publications, disciplines, communities, and the originating universities.

Q13. Do you agree that next to some basic metrics (e.g., times viewed, downloads) the platform should support and highlight article(or document)-level metrics, possibly via altmetrics (such as social media discussions)?

9 out of 11 universities have responded yes to this question, while 2/11 have responded no.

The explanation of the positive respondents:

- General:
 - Our policy encourages showcasing a variety of metrics. We prefer to raise awareness and increase metrics literacy rather than censoring or not displaying existing information.
 - The problem with altmetrics is that not all disciplines are equally present on social media or produce content that is suitable for social media. This potentially introduces inequalities. In addition to altmetrics, valid indicators could perhaps be citation counts. However, how to implement this without relying on Scopus or WoS is an issue.
 - Altmetrics should not be used in place of traditional metrics, but rather in addition to them in order to get a better understanding of the research in a wider context.
 - We plan on using Overton for public policy impact.
 - There's obviously a difference between capturing such metrics and using them for rewards, which is very discipline-specific.
 - We use altmetrics in research assessment and policy.
- Metrics as a filter or tool for readers:
 - Publication outputs need to be pre-filtered for the potential reader. View frequencies are proxies for broader interest, and if imperfect, still useful for highlighting published titles.
 - Authors and visitors can use altmetrics to find related and necessary information about output and can make a judgement about the quality and the societal and academic impact.
 - These metrics can show how the documents are receiving attention.
- Metrics for research community itself:
 - it is a need for researchers (for their career), for the University (for research evaluation, to establish new partnerships, and to monitor its open science policy)

Lund University	Y
University of Freiburg	Y
Universiteit Leiden	Y
University of Amsterdam	Y
Utrecht University	Y
KU Leuven	Y
Sorbonne University	Y
University Paris-Saclay	Y
University of Strasbourg	Y
Université de Genève	N
University of Zurich	Y
University of Barcelona	Y
University of Helsinki	N
Trinity College Dublin	Y
University of Milan	Y
University of Edinburgh	Y

The respondents with a 'no':

- Altmetrics are yet another kind of metrics. Too many metrics.

- The national repository HAL is meant to make articles available for free. No metric has been envisaged yet.

Q14. What ‘framework(s) for recognition and rewards’ are implemented by your university for research evaluation?

13 universities have responded to this question:

- Four universities have not (yet) a framework in place:
 - We have just signed DORA and joined the European coalition COARA.
 - The University does not specify a generally binding overall framework for research evaluation. However, several regulations have been set up for particular cases, such as for professional appointments or tenure evaluations, which take into account a broader spectrum of research output, or even impact than pure metrics.
 - The University is planning to evolve its monitoring tool for scientific production and associated indicators in order to further integrate open science indicators to the report, in the context of discussions on rewarding efforts on open science.
 - A specific report is under review and our University will probably adopt the measures recommended in that report.
- Nine universities have a framework in place:
 - Metrics are used when relevant and always in a [responsible way](#).
 - In November 2019, the Dutch UNL, NFU, KNAW, NWO and ZonMw have published the position paper [Room for everyone’s talent](#): towards a new balance in the recognition and rewards for academics in which they indicate how to aim to more broadly recognise and reward the work of academic staff. This includes placing less emphasis on the number of publications, and a greater emphasis on the other domains in which the academic is active, such as education and impact. See also the policy on [university level](#).
 - [Declaration](#) that recommends explicitly an “nuanced approach” to interpreting metrics and the impact factor. There is also an [attempt](#) to align professional hiring practices with open science academic practices.
 - The University adopted a [single document on Open Science](#) which details its OS policy. The encouragement of the careful use of new bibliometric indicators is one of its objectives.
 - The University has a [Recognition and Reward Programme](#) with five focus areas: (1) Develop quality assessment of education, research, societal relevance and teamwork; (2) Develop a portfolio model as the basis for the annual interview or P&D interview; (3) Develop a substantiated CV for appointments and promotions; (4) Develop a transparent policy for appointments, permanent appointments and promotions for all academic staff positions; (5) Adjust the profile of managers (focused more on connecting, social competences and collaboration). The intention is that this should ultimately lead to a better balance in careers and quality assessment, where attention is also paid to teaching and collaborations. The recognition and reward system in the Netherlands is the [Strategy Evaluation Protocol 2021](#) with three main assessment criteria 1) research quality, 2) societal relevance and 3) viability. The use of the Journal Impact Factor is not allowed. The use of individual bibliometric indicators such as the h-index is strongly discouraged.
 - Promotion system, from tenure track and assistant professor to associate professor/professor, with research as a central component.
 - Currently, the research evaluation is performed mainly using traditional journal-based metrics. However, the University is committed to change this framework and implement it.
 - We have implemented DORA and COARA.

Q15. Which 'metrics' to 'measure' success should be incorporated by the platform?

There are two respondents who think that the platform should have no metrics. One explanation of this viewpoint: 'the primary function of the platform should be making academic knowledge easily open access for all in all stages of the research. Measuring success in relation to research evaluation is not necessary'.

A few other respondents plead for a combination of traditional and new (open science) metrics. Another respondent only mentions open science metrics while one respondent suggested citation counts as the only metric. Finally, one respondent finds that only metrics should be incorporated by the platform that are robust, reproducible, and transparent.

Q16. In what other ways can the platform contribute to an evolving system of research evaluation?

The responses to this question are rather varied:

- By not using journal-based metrics for marketing the platform.
- Uniform dissemination and indexing of all kinds of research output
- A key issue with current systems is that they are mainly centred on the scientific written publications as the key scientific output. This disregards other outputs, such as software or data, that may be equally or even more impactful,
- Highlight the diversity of research output, other than publications. Highlight research outputs other than publications. Highlight collaborative research. Display a narrative to explain why this output is highlighted.
- If the platform is intended as a common tool for universities in the international arena, it is possible that it would facilitate the recruitment of experts for panels used in research evaluations
- The platform should be flexible. Most important is the use of open standards and trying to connect the systems that are not yet easy to connect with, such as policy documents/decisions and the media. It also has to connect to evaluation systems. The connections should be available for all output types: not only for peer-reviewed articles.
- It could incorporate open peer review, i.e., outputs and activities could be open to ongoing comments, input, and advice to improve the value and assessment of those outputs.

A few common denominators can be derived from these answers: the diversity of research output and in the slipstream of this, the importance of research outputs that are not publications are seen as possible important contributions of the platform.

4. QUALITY ASSURANCE AND CONTROL

The quality of scholarly work disseminated through a public infrastructure should be ensured. Different standards can apply depending on the particular type of scholarly output that is being assessed, as well as the context in which it is assessed. Universities have different local policies to be respected.

Q17. If your university has a local publication platform (repository/publishing platforms) for research data, publications, journals and/or other research outputs, what kind of quality assurance and control do you have in place? What are the good and bad practices?

One respondent gives a general answer that seems to reflect the answers by the other respondents:

- The issue of academic quality remains with the researchers. The library and its data curators focus on formal checks, such as metadata quality, formats, licences, completeness of documents. When it comes to content issues (such as integrity of data quality, protection of privacy, academic integrity of articles et cetera) researchers and editors are ‘legally’ responsible. To clarify responsibilities and liabilities, we have dedicated agreements to be signed or at least digitally agree to.

The other responses can be summarised as follows:

- **Regarding repositories/CRIS systems:**
 - metadata are validated before publication; 5 respondents
 - metadata are validated after publication
 - most publications have undergone peer review procedures established by publishers
 - quality control is operated by librarians upon deposit by authors
 - quality control on metadata, licensing, authorship, some control on plagiarism
 - for PhD dissertations a plagiarism checker is in place
 - for the French national repository HAL, a three-level approach is described: at a national level, moderation to control the quality of metadata and the legal aspects; at the institutional level, regularly checks and corrections of metadata (especially for the name of the research units), and at the research unit level, a ‘HAL point of contact’ that makes first level corrections and/or list metadata errors.
 - Each record is controlled and validated by the staff. Each PDF in the repository is verified for copyright.
 - Checks on and enhancing metadata are being made.
- **Regarding (journal) publication platforms:**
 - in the hands of the editorial teams of the journals; 2 respondents
 - Lund University reports the University press publishing open access monographs within the Humanities using peer review.
 - The University press operates according to the COPE principles.
- **Regarding research data infrastructures:**
 - metadata are validated before publication; 2 respondents
 - curation of the dataset before publication: 5 respondents
 - automatic quality control of file formats
 - a quality check of data and metadata has been implemented; 2 respondents.

Lund University	Y
University of Freiburg	Y
Universiteit Leiden	Y
University of Amsterdam	Y
Utrecht University	Y
KU Leuven	Y
Sorbonne University	Y
University Paris-Saclay	Y
University of Strasbourg	Y
Université de Genève	Y
University of Zurich	Y
University of Barcelona	Y
University of Helsinki	Y
Trinity College Dublin	Y
University of Milan	Y
University of Edinburgh	Y

Two respondents have reacted to the good and bad practice question:

- **Bad practices:** (1) Not using persistent identifiers such as DOI's; (2) Registering, uploading, checking, and controlling takes a lot of time of researchers and support staff; (3) Rejections at a later stage: with open licenses it gets difficult to reach all places where files may appear and inform the reader.
- **Good practice:** Tools to check and find DOI's of the reference lists.

Q18. The platform should deliver transparency on the process of quality control and allow several levels of and approaches to quality assurance. Do you agree?

Ten universities filled out this question. Nine answered with yes with the following arguments:

- Different research outputs have different quality control mechanisms, procedures, and responsible parties.
- There can be different levels of and approaches to quality assurance depending on the type of publication and the academic discipline. The effort should not be directed to trying to make this more uniform but should be directed at making clear for each item how the quality assurance was handled.
- There is no one size fits all. It depends on the research output type and of the practices within the discipline. Nevertheless, it should be possible to define a minimum set of basic quality standards that are common across disciplines.
- Transparency will contribute to research integrity. In addition, both administrative checks and quality control are necessary to guarantee that published items meet the minimum requirements of the University and conform with all laws and regulations such as GDPR.
- The platform should allow for quality assurance by the research units that have a collection in the open repository and the institution managing the portal.
- If we would engage with such a platform, it will be the chance to experiment with open and more inclusive peer review models.
- The end user of the product should be able to judge quality based on the information available on the platform (two respondents).

One respondent did not reply to the yes/no question but used the following argument:

- The validity of the data as well as the validity of the research process is under the responsibility of the authors and the responsibility of the journals for published articles.

Q19. If the public infrastructure offers a form of quality control, should the quality control process be the same for all types of output? Think of traditional types of output such as academic articles, books, and book chapters, but also of research data, protocols, software and code, teaching materials (e.g., textbooks), other educational materials, audio-visual material, slides, posters, etc.

Most respondents answered no, while some ignored the yes/no part of the question.

- Most respondent state that the quality assurance should be handled differently for each type of publication.
- One respondent states: 'We are still in a learning phase. Nevertheless, it is clear that data creation for research data is much more time-consuming as expected. In addition, close cooperation with research is needed'.

- One respondent states that the metadata should address the F of findability and the A of accessibility of the FAIR definition.
- Another respondent states that administrators and quality checks necessarily differ across items. Text can be subject to copyright, data cannot. Access to data can be regulated through RDX, but RDX conditions must then be checked. Data must also be checked for FAIR requirements and for conforming to laws and regulations.
- one respondent states that different processes will be required for different types of output. Research data may require special skills to determine if they are properly anonymized and renderable.
- Finally, one respondent suggests offering the same kind of review options for all output types, however with different templates with questions.

Q20. What kind of control is necessary for authors to publish via public infrastructures?

Answer categories (multiple choices were possible)	Responses
Not any	1
Administrative (e.g., metadata, licence, plagiarism)	12
Peer review (internal or external)	1
Administrative and peer reviewed (internal or external)	2

Table 1 Type of controls seen as necessary for public infrastructures

The answers to this question are presented in table 1.

A few additional comments:

- Academic quality checks, peer review et cetera good from our point of view will follow later, independently. To be organised by traditional publishers or by communities itself.
- Public publication infrastructures should have the technical capability to organise quality control procedures via the platform. However, there should not be a compulsion to perform a quality control procedure for every object with the exception of a limited set of administrated metadata.
- The respondent who ticked the box of 'not any': peer review is not necessary to share output. The idea of the open public infrastructure is to share as open and as early as possible. There are many initiatives to review preprints such as PCI. The Notify project is working on an international standard to connect repositories and peer review services.
- A respondent who ticked all the boxes: it depends on what you want to achieve with the public infrastructure. If you wish to compete with traditional publishers, then both administrative control and peer review will be necessary. However, if one particularly aims at non-traditional publications and/or wishes to favour innovation, one could limit it to admin control or combine prepublication administrative control with post-publication peer-review.
- The French respondents remarked that the national repository HAL works according to the principle of technical validation which consists in verifying that the file is conform and the metadata correctly filled. Part of the publications preprints, part is reviewed journal articles. There is support for PCI, a system where scientific communities take the responsibility of reviewing articles.
- As a minimum, any public outputs should have metadata that makes them FAIR. Some outputs may require peer-review, particularly if they have the potential to be misused or to (mis)-inform health policy et cetera.
- These categories seem problematic; certainly, plagiarism check is usually not an administrative/automated application, but an essential part of peer review.

Q21. What kinds of quality control are necessary for publications before being disseminated through a public infrastructure? Is this ‘must have’ [M], ‘should have’ [S], ‘could have’ [C] or ‘won’t have’ [W]?

Answer categories (only one choice was possible)	Must have	Should have	Could have	Won't have
plagiarism check	4	5	4	
laws and regulations (privacy, security, AVG compliant etc.)	10	1	2	
curation of research data check	3	9	1	
interoperability of research data check	4	4	5	
internal academic quality control by local editorial board	3	1	6	3
form of editorial / desk review by the platform	2		8	2
peer review	1	2	8	2

Table 2 Quality control seen as necessary before dissemination via a public infrastructure

The results are presented in table 2. If we combine ‘must have’ and ‘should have’, the checks on laws and regulations and the curation of research data score highest, followed by a check on plagiarism and a check on the curation of research data. The other options score much lower.

Q22. If you think peer review is necessary for (some) publication types using a public infrastructure, what kind of peer review should be provided?

Answer categories (multiple choices were possible)	Responses
closed pre-publication peer review	0
open pre-publication peer review	3
closed post-publication peer review	0
open post-publication peer review	6
flexibility to choose between pre- or post-publication peer review	5
flexibility to choose between open and closed peer review	5
flexibility to choose between no peer review and some sort of peer review	5
no peer review needed	2

Table 3 Necessity of types of peer review for public infrastructures according to the respondents

The results are presented in table 3. These results reflect the answers given to Q20: many respondents support the idea of ‘publish first, review later’ for public infrastructures.

Two comments:

‘The landscape of scientific publication is changing rapidly, the emergence of preprint archives, the possibility of publishing reviews are new and important elements that foreshadow new developments in a hitherto closed and concealed system’.

‘Post-publication peer review depends on reviewers actually taking the time to provide constructive feedback; this is never guaranteed. Open pre-publication peer review ensures some level of quality control, with open peer review ensuring that the quality of the review itself is improved (compared to closed peer review).’

Q23. Which networks (ethics, research integrity) should a public infrastructure aspire to join?

Answer categories	Responses
Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE)	10
Catalogue of Open Infrastructure Services (COIs)	7
ALLEA code of conduct	9

Table 4 Networks for a public infrastructure to join

The results are presented in table 4. Some respondents suggested additional networks to join:

- OASPA
- STM
- DFG code of conduct DFG code of conduct: [Guidelines for safeguarding good scientific research practice](#)

5. PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION

Open Science fosters cooperative work and new ways of distributing knowledge by openly sharing and dynamically exchanging research outcomes. Several stakeholders need to be involved using different guidelines and regulations. This has consequences for practical implementation of the public infrastructure, think of for example archiving, deleting, and retracting.

Q24. If your university has infrastructures for open data, publications (repository/publishing platforms), journals and other research outputs, please state which stakeholders (library, support services, researchers etc.) are responsible for the tasks mentioned below.

Lund University	Y
University of Freiburg	Y
Universiteit Leiden	Y
University of Amsterdam	Y
Utrecht University	Y
KU Leuven	Y
Sorbonne University	Y
University Paris-Saclay	Y
University of Strasbourg	Y
Université de Genève	Y
University of Zurich	Y
University of Barcelona	Y
University of Helsinki	Y
Trinity College Dublin	N
University of Milan	N
University of Edinburgh	Y

	Workflow management	Dissemination and discovery	Authentication, authorisation, and access	Research data management (screening, FAIR)	Next generation metrics	Long-term preservation
Library	11	10	7	10	4	9
IT department	2	2	7	4	2	8
Editorial staff/ University press	3	2	1			1
Faculty	2		1	3	1	
Researchers		1		4	1	1
HAL/CINES	2	1			1	3
Research support services	1			2		
Support services for Open Science (in the Quality Assurance Unit)	1	1	1	1	1	1
Communication Department		1				
University management/central administration			1		2	
University archive						1
Research office					1	
Automated service	1		1			
Data service provider		1	1			
Nobody					2	

Table 5 Stakeholders involved in 6 tasks in 14 universities

The answers are summarised in Appendix A. In table 5, the results of the scoring of the answers are presented from the answers of 14 universities (some respondents mentioned more than 1 stakeholder for a particular task). A few observations from this table:

- The task 'next generation metrics' is the only task with two universities answering 'nobody', while the responses of the other universities vary.
- The library is the most mentioned stakeholder with regard to workflow management, dissemination and discovery and research data management.
- The IT department and the library are mentioned more or less equally frequently with regard to authentication, authorisation, and access and with regard to long-term preservation.
- Other stakeholders are mentioned by some respondents, reflecting the different research environments and responsibilities between universities.

One of the respondents makes an additional remark: 'As for data we foresee the need of access committees for data that has been deposited in the closed contracts, for authors that can't be contacted any more or in cases of potential deletion of published data'.

Q25. How do you deal with long-term archiving in your current infrastructures?

- The French universities point to CINES, a national organisation for long-term preservation of documents. One respondent adds that for research data, the long-term preservation is not yet organised but there might be a role for CINES here too.
- Dutch universities point to the e-depot of the Royal Library of the Netherlands for publications. One University states that the datasets are stored for at least 10 years, ISO certified server in Europe via the provider Figshare. Another University mentions the DANS organisation (Data Archiving and Networked Services) and the 4TU.ResearchData repository. The third Dutch university states that its data repository (based on inhouse developed software) secures long-term archiving.
- The University of Zurich has multiple backups of the content of its repository that are locally distributed. The journal platform uses LOCKSS and the data repository SWISSUbase aims at being Seal Core Trusted.
- Each publication in the repository/publication platform of Freiburg is stored for a long term in the archive system of the University computing centre. Checksums (md5) ensure the integrity of the archived data and the originality of the published data. A second copy is stored elsewhere. Documents that are reported to the German National library are additionally archived there for the long-term.
- The possibility for mid-term archiving is in progress, digital long-term archiving as possible via the National service provider CSC.
- At other universities the long-term preservation is differently organised or in the process of being organised:
 - 'Our CRIS is not designed to meet the demands stipulated in the archives act. Faculties have their own guidelines. The University archive offers support regarding some aspects'.
 - Currently the infrastructures are preserved through backups. The consortium is working on long-term preservation.
 - With regard to RDM, a general collection, creation and preservation plan will be ready by 2024.
 - 'We are establishing a data centre'.
 - 'There is a digital archivist and a digital preservation working group in the library. Service owners are responsible for the sustainability of their infrastructure.'

Q26. Do you have any suggestions how a public infrastructure should deal with long-term archiving?

Many respondents emphasise the importance of long-term preservation for public infrastructure. Suggestions are:

- Aligning to the CoreTrustSeal requirements
- One solution could be that the local setup/University is responsible for the archiving and that a LOCKSS network ensure the long-term preservation
- Responsibility for long-term archiving should be in the same scope as ownership of the content.
- Specialised infrastructures are required for non-traditional, non-linear forms of data and code publication to allow later reuse and reproduction. Such infrastructures need to preserve the necessary context of former research, so that data can be reproduced in its original setting if necessary. Long-term access to software is a significant challenge, technically and legally. Such infrastructural requirements are presently discussed within the national research data infrastructure in Germany.
- Make use of services such as Portico, LOCKSS, JASPER or Dataverse
- Making an agreement with CINES
- Setting up a consortium of several academic stakeholders.
- There should be long-term preservation at a national level.
- Use a federated system of institutional repositories.
- Someone has to be assigned the data owner.

Q27. Research data may have a retention period. What should happen with the metadata after the retention period of a data set in a related system expires after 5-10 years?

Many respondents stated that the metadata must be kept beyond the retention period of the dataset. This is also part of the OAIS standard.

Other responses:

- In the national repository of France, any dataset is stored for five years and possibly for an extended period if solid arguments are provided. Long-term archiving is the responsibility of the universities.
- The University will provide researchers with an infrastructure to archive and share data for a period of 10 years. For long-term archiving, third-party solutions which comply with the CoreTrustSeal will be used.
- If the data management plans provide archiving for only 5 to 10 years, archiving beyond this period is not required.
- Metadata must remain archived.

Q28. The public platform should be made interoperable with other open infrastructures such as [OPENAIRE](#), [COAR Notify](#) and [EOSC](#). Please list the infrastructures that are the most important with which the planned infrastructure should be interoperable.

Apart from the infrastructures mentioned in the question itself, respondents listed a number of other options:

- The platform should be connected to local infrastructures, to supra-regional infrastructures and to national and international library catalogues and to ORCID. Furthermore, the publication should be listed in bibliographic databases and be findable via Internet search engines.

- ArXiv
- CERIF
- CESSDA
- COAR Notify Protocol (when it is available)
- Crossref
- DANS
- Dariah
- Dart Europe
- EOSC Provider Requirements (e.g., EOSC AAI, EOSC Core); EOSC PID policy
- ERICs
- Europeana
- I4OC
- I4OA
- Internet Archive
- Google
- Google dataset search
- Google scholar
- HAL
- MODS-DIDL
- NARCIS (the Netherlands)
- OpenAIRE Research Graph
- ORCID
- PubMed
- RDG
- RE3Data
- software heritage

European Open Science Cloud: *The ambition of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is to develop a 'Web of FAIR Data and Services' for science and research in Europe. EOSC will be a multi-disciplinary environment where researchers can publish, find and re-use data, and use tools and services, enabling them better to conduct their work.*

Q29. How should we ensure that the aim and functions of EOSC are not duplicated by the platform, but rather complemented?

A number of respondents mention active participation in EOSC:

- Through the EOSC task forces, which are currently actively discussing these topics.
- It is necessary that the platform is connected to EOSC and that universities with such platforms have an EOSC membership.
- Taking an active part in the development of EOSC
- The platform should follow the EOSC standards in order to be harvested and some of the contents be available through EOSC.
- This is a challenge but absolutely crucial for the suggested platform to take into account. Since we don't know the EOSC position in 10 years, it is hard to speculate about possible duplicated challenges. The EOSC infrastructure, its members, local projects et cetera could be used as a driver and setting up new dissemination infrastructures.
- Closer collaboration with EOSC

- University repositories should be consolidated on a national level, together with an Open Knowledge Base. National infrastructures and international infrastructures and Open Knowledge Bases should be connected to EOSC or even consolidated into the EOSC.
- Be aware of existing infrastructures and services in the EOSC marketplace (at the moment 364) and what is done in the ongoing projects e.g., INFRAEOSC07-projects (- C-Scale, EUDAT-DICE, EGI-ACE, OpenAIRE-Nexus, RELIANCE) and what ERICs are developing and planning to develop.

Other suggestions are:

- By structuring the links, among others at national level, between local, national and EOSC platforms.
- Work on maximising interoperability and good metadata. If it can be found (metadata) and used (interoperability) through PID's can be linked to and ingested in several connected platforms.
- Following the design paradigms of FAIR data points, with deep functionality for its research and analyses apps can be built upon [FAIR data points can be used to describe datasets in a FAIR way, using standard metadata and make them available through simple WWWprotocols.
- We believe that competition leads to better services. A certain amount of redundancy should be encouraged.
- Perhaps focus more on research communities and community-driven elements/issues. Another approach would be to think about priorities: from this perspective one perhaps has to focus on publications.
- One respondent states that there are more players to consider than just EOSC, such as the Open Research Europe platform and domain specific research infrastructures, such as Operas. This means that duplication will be hard to prevent unless considerable effort goes into consultation with the different parties. Interoperability is core in this context. As long as we can guarantee interoperability on multiple aspects to exchange with these other platforms, the initiative for an own platform is viable and potential duplication is less of an issue.

One respondent gives an elaborate answer, making the following points:

- EOSC is not a single place of platform, it is an ecosystem. The EOSC Association and projects are developing high level services (single sign on, discoverability layers, etc) but this doesn't work unless the layer at the bottom is accessing, preparing, depositing the products of their research. In the DARIAH context, our national nodes make the services developed in their local contexts visible. We don't host their data, but we do provide a contextualised discovery layer that is also visible through the EOSC portal.
- The OpenAIRE model is an excellent way to reduce duplication and support sustainability. This model utilises local and/or distributed deposit of content using institutional and subject repositories (including Zenodo), the application of agreed standards and identifiers at the local level, the harvesting of metadata and/or content either in whole or using agreed selection criteria. The model enables the best of all worlds: local applications can be maintained supporting local cultures and priorities; quality and standards are presented via harvesting or direct deposit at the aggregate/platform level; a repository is available for institutions/researchers who may not have an available / suitable institutional repository. OpenAIRE also provides the OpenAIRE Research Community Gateway – an overlay platform making it easy to share, link, disseminate and monitor all of a country's, group of institutions or research project's publications, data, software, methods. In one place, see: <https://www.openaire.eu/research-community-gateway-guide>
- By collaborating with EOSC/OpenAIRE and complementing its services, the platform will avoid duplication.

6. COPYRIGHT, LICENSING AND DATA PROTECTION

Intellectual property (IP) legislation and policies can differ per country, university, and output type. Funders and institutions can demand the use of certain internally-accepted licences (such as Creative Commons). In an open public infrastructure authors and universities have to decide under what conditions they publish their output and what rights they would like to grant to the users. Users need to be informed on user rights (attribution, reuse, commercial use, derivatives, etc.).

Q30. Does your university have a policy on the use of open licences for content? If so, provide a link and a short description of the policy.

15 universities have responded to these questions. Most do not have a formal policy of the use of open licences for content, A few comments were made:

- One respondent links to a web page with a description of the various licences: <https://www.helsinki.fi/en/helsinki-university-library/library-researchers/open-science-services/copyright-and-licenses>
- In our new OA policy, we expect from researchers that they will publish using an open licence to enhance reuse (ask but no mandate).
- CC licences are adopted for data and for articles and books. We suggest CC BY SA that authors are free to choose a more restrictive license.
- The University has an intellectual property policy which does not mention open licences. The policy is not yet published.
- We do not have a policy yet but incite researchers to take a CC licence on their articles and datasets.
- The Dutch team that negotiates Read & Publish agreements asks for CC-BY by default.
- The University does have an open access policy encouraging publishing in open access. However specific specifications for the use of licences are not stated. The funding of APCs via OA-fund however is linked to the expectation that CC-BY licences are preferably chosen.
- Many use CC licences but preferences vary between disciplines and depend on which licences journals offer.
- One respondent offers a link to the choice of data and software licenses for their data repository: (<https://www.kuleuven.be/rdm/en/rdr/licenses>) but researchers are free to use other available licenses.
- The University of Zurich expects its researchers and staff to publish all the scholarly output open access in their [open science policy](#).
- We apply the CC-BY-NC-SA licence as default to all content (including electronic theses and datasets) deposited in TARA, but we offer a choice at the deposit stage of the full range of CC licences. The 'NC' licence is recommended by TCD in order to encourage commercial entities to contact the author/s for permission/information purposes before re-using. This is important information for author economic impact reporting purposes (otherwise we would have no way to capture information on commercial re-use). There is a concern, especially in the area of Open Educational Resources, about the aggregation and monetisation of OA content by some opportunistic commercial agencies.
- The [policy](#) is focussed on copyright relating to publications. Upon acceptance of publication, each staff member with a responsibility for research agrees to grant the University of Edinburgh a non-exclusive, irrevocable, worldwide licence to make manuscripts of their scholarly articles publicly available under the terms of a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence, or a more permissive licence. This policy applies to all scholarly articles, including conference proceedings,

Lund University	Y
University of Freiburg	Y
Universiteit Leiden	Y
University of Amsterdam	Y
Utrecht University	Y
KU Leuven	Y
Sorbonne University	Y
University Paris-Saclay	Y
University of Strasbourg	Y
Université de Genève	N
University of Zurich	Y
University of Barcelona	Y
University of Helsinki	Y
Trinity College Dublin	Y
University of Milan	Y
University of Edinburgh	Y

authored or co-authored while the person is a staff member of The University of Edinburgh. Whilst the policy does not apply to monographs, scholarly editions, textbooks, book chapters, collections of essays, datasets, or other outputs that are not scholarly articles, the University strongly encourages researchers to make them as openly available as possible.

Q31. What are considered appropriate licences for publications such as texts, (meta)data, teaching materials, etc. and other outputs that will be published at your university?

	none	CC BY	CC BY-SA	CC BY-ND	CC BY-NC	CC BY-NC-SA	CC BY-NC-ND	CC0
Articles		7	3	2	3	2	2	
books & book chapters		6	3	2	3 ⁶	3	1	
Reports		4	1		1	1	1	
data announcement	2	5	2		1			1
protocols ⁷	1	2			1	1		
software code ⁸	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1
teaching materials	1	4	1	1	2	2	1	1
Textbooks	1	4	1	1	2	2	1	
audio-visual material (in general)	1	3			1	1		1
slides (in general)	1	4	1	1	2	2		1
Metadata		2	1					5

Table 6 Appropriate licenses per type of research output

The answers to this question are presented in table 6. One comment: ‘Although many people believe CC0 is best for research data, we have found a default CC-BY licence is very popular with our depositors and reassures them that they won’t get ‘poached’.’

⁶ For books only, not for book chapters

⁷ According to one respondent, this is not applicable.

⁸ With regard to software licenses, MIT, GNU, Apache and Open-Source Licenses (opensource.org/licenses) are additionally suggested. One respondent remarks in addition: software code is often developed from scratch. If not, the license of the source code it is built on needs to be taken into account.

Q32 Who is the copyright holder within your university and who should be able to grant a licence for publication on the platform?

	Who is the Copyright holder?		Who should be able to grant a licence?		
	Researcher	University	Researcher	University	Researcher on behalf of the University
articles	7	2	5		1
books & book chapters	7	2	5	2	1
reports	7	2	5	1	1
data announcement	7	2	5	1	1
protocols	4	2	5	1	1
Software code	3	5	3	3	1
teaching materials	5	3	4	2	1
textbooks	5	3	4	2	1
audio-visual material (in general)	6	3	4	2	1
Slides (in general)	6	3	4	1	1
metadata	1	1	3	1	

Table 7 Copyright holders of types of research output

The answers to this question are presented in table 7. The boxes about the copyright holder are filled out by seven universities, the second question only by a few respondents. Remarks are:

- To my understanding only the copyright holder can grant a licence.
- Unable to give a general answer. The type 'articles' for example is supposed to be trivial. But it is not! Depending on the community or on the editors, they sometimes prefer a CC BY-NC-ND licence. The colleagues in the library try to recommend licences as open as possible but often without success.
- One respondent explains the copyright situation in the HE sector of Germany elaborately:
 - The German copyright law distinguishes between moral rights (§§ 12-14 UrhG), exploitation rights (§§ 15-24) and rights of use (§§ 31-44). The moral right includes the right of publication (§ 12), the right to recognition of authorship (§ 13) and the right to prohibit distortion of the work (§ 14). Moral rights are usually not transferable under German law and remain in the possession of the author.
 - The principle that in the case of employed authors the exclusive rights of use lie with the employer applies only to a limited extent in the university sector. Who has the exclusive rights of use depends in the German university sector on the activity performed. Full professors, honorary professors, visiting professors, university lecturers and lecturers work without instructions and on their own responsibility. On the basis of the freedom of science and research guaranteed in the Basic Law for the Federal Republic of Germany (Art. 5(3) GG), they own all rights to their copyrighted works. However, insofar as scientists write copyright-protected works in the course of their official duties, the

university may be entitled to rights of use in these works on the basis of the nature of the employment relationship (so-called official works). According to general opinion, teaching, and research, but not the publication of research results, belong to the official duties of university scientists. Works of service are therefore to be assumed primarily in the case of lecture materials, but not in the case of research publications or textbooks.

- Scientific assistants/staff or student employees are usually subject to the professional responsibility of a university teacher within the framework of an employment and service relationship. They therefore act in accordance with instructions. Although they are entitled to the copyright to the copyrighted works they create, the rights of use are granted to the university as the employer for use and exploitation (Section 43 UrhG). Scientific assistants / employees or student employees who perform non-instructional scientific work, such as doctoral students, post-doctoral students, and diploma students, may freely dispose of the rights of use to the dissertations, post-doctoral theses, and diploma theses as authors of their works. The university therefore has no right of use.
- If the university wishes to exploit works for which no rights of use exist, it must conclude a license agreement with the respective author.
- A special feature applies to computer programs. If software is developed within the scope of an employment relationship, the employer alone is entitled to use it.
- Remark with regard to software code: the licence holder could be 1/3 party if the commercial or other contract is in place.
- Remark with regard to report: it is possible that the report is owned by a commissioning agency.
- In Ireland, the national legislation confirms the employer (the institution) as the copyright owner of works created during employment. However, the University does not accept its ownership but instead states in its IPR policy that publications are owned by the authors. All other types of outputs, including data, are owned by the University.

7. CLOSING QUESTIONS

Q33. Do you as a LERU member use open publication platform(s) which you feel meet the standard of a digital sovereign public infrastructure as envisioned by LERU's Public Infrastructure Taskforce?

- HAL
- Zenodo
- Peer Community In
- OpenEdition
- Open Research Europe
- Openjournals.nl
- Welcome platform
- PubPub
- the Swedish repository for research data, DORIS
- Open Science Framework; University of Edinburgh DataShare
- Islandora

Lund University	Y
University of Freiburg	Y
Universiteit Leiden	Y
University of Amsterdam	Y
Utrecht University	Y
KU Leuven	Y
Sorbonne University	Y
University Paris-Saclay	Y
University of Strasbourg	Y
Université de Genève	N
University of Zurich	Y
University of Barcelona	N
University of Helsinki	Y
Trinity College Dublin	Y
University of Milan	Y
University of Edinburgh	Y

Q34. Do you as a LERU member know open publication platform(s) which you feel meet the standard of a digital sovereign public infrastructure as envisioned by LERU's Public Infrastructure Taskforce?

- Several national diamond open access publishing platforms would seem to meet the digital sovereign public infrastructure as envisioned by LERU's Public Infrastructure Taskforce. Examples are the open publishing platforms in Finland, the Netherlands, Scotland, Croatia (etc.). Redalyc is the outstanding international example and supports the AmeliCA Principles.
- Open Journal Systems (OJS) is the widely-used open-source publishing management system used to support many of the platforms above. Also of potential in this area are the Coko Foundation open-source resources and services <https://coko.foundation/>
- OpenAIRE's infrastructure and services support these and other OA content providers, harvesting, showcasing, and providing analytics on the content. OpenAIRE would seem to meet the digital sovereign public infrastructure as envisioned by LERU's Public Infrastructure Taskforce.
- DSpace CRIS is used to support institutional and cross-institutional platforms and services. It is open source, well-governed and well-supported.
- OpenEdition
- <https://www.science-ouverte.cnrs.fr/plateformes-dedition-ouverte/>
- [Next Generation Library Publishing 2022](#)
- Openjournals.nl
- OPERAS
- Openjournals.nl
- Manifold would be a more than capable project for the PIT's ambitions: <https://manifoldapp.org/>. Manifold is an open-source publishing and annotation platform designed to be self-hosted, which would maintain a certain level of digital sovereignty. Installed on our own servers, data of platform users would not be collected or surveilled by outside parties.
- PubPub would also be an interesting solution: [PubPub · Community Publishing](#). While PubPub is centrally hosted, its parent non-profit organization, Knowledge Futures Group, commits itself to limited data monitoring.

- [Octopus](#) is also interesting to look at. The current repository structure, combined with the Notify project is also an option.
- Research equals <https://www.researchequals.com/> could be interesting but is still developing.
- The organizational model of OAPEN can be interesting as OAPEN provides services for publishers, libraries, and research funders in the areas of deposit, dissemination, quality assurance, metadata enhancement and digital preservation.
- Multidisciplinary infrastructures (publication platforms, repositories, publishing services):
 - Repository of the Leibniz Association: <https://www.leibnizopen.de/>
 - Berlin Universities Publishing, a distributed network for publishing services, <https://www.berlin-university-alliance.de/en/commitments/sharing-resources/dnps/index.html>, <https://www.berlin-universities-publishing.de/>
 - Coalition of Diamond Open Access Publishing (COAP), concept of an international support network for the publication of Diamond Open Access Journals, contact: Helge Steenweg, Stuttgart University Library
 - Zenodo
- Disciplinary infrastructures (publication platforms, repositories, publishing services):
 - “Arxiv’s”: Arxiv.org, BioRxiv, MedRxiv
 - Repository of the Zentralbibliothek Wirtschaft, Kiel (economics): <https://www.econstor.eu/>
 - Repository of ZBMed, Köln (life sciences, medicine) <https://www.publisso.de/>
 - OA publishing infrastructures of the German FIDs (Fachinformationsdienste): <https://www.linguistik.de/en/about/news/fid-linguistik-supports-open-access-as-publication-model/>
 - Repositories of the National Research Data Infrastructure Germany (NFDI) (<https://nfdi4culture.de/resources/repositories.html>)
- ScholarLed and COPIM were also mentioned, although not being a platform as such.

Q35. Are there any other issues that are relevant for a public infrastructure that you would like to share?

Five remarks:

- The quickest win would actually be to not conceive a new infrastructure with its own organisation and governance, but to create an alliance of existing, mission alliance initiatives.
- We experienced several of the questions asked in the survey to leave quite a lot of space for interpretations and hence difficult to respond to. Although we do find the idea of digital sovereignty worldwide and therefore for any University valuable.
- We want to move to a new reward and recognition system, but to be able to do that we need an infrastructure that supports more output types and other ways of publishing. The public infrastructure can help to change the system.
- As mentioned earlier, a public research infrastructure should act as an aggregator of, and discovery platform for, institutional CRIS content. This should be capable of

importing/harvesting from the vast number of university-based CRIS and possibly also provide a CRIS for institutions that don't have one. Agreed standards and selection criteria would underpin this element of the platform plus links to the open access versions of research outputs. Emphasis should be on avoiding duplication and on revealing research activity in a comprehensive way, representing, and supporting bibliodiversity and (at the very least) the full range of research outputs from all disciplines. Only when this information is reliably and consistently available can the extent and growth of open research be truly understood and supported.

- An interoperable federation from institutions may be more practical than an overarching (top-down) infrastructure and would keep expertise and commitment within the institution.

And a respondent with a list of links:

- See <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7028253> for the original PIT charter.
- <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/03/europe-digital-sovereignty/>
- [Pooley, J., \(2022\) "Surveillance Publishing", The Journal of Electronic Publishing 25\(1\), https://doi.org/10.3998/jep.1874](#); [Ioridi, L. \(2020\)](#)
- The Fight for Digital Sovereignty: What It Is, and Why It Matters, Especially for the EU. *Philosophy & Technology* (33), 369–378 , <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-020-00423-6>;
- Jansen, D., (19 October 2021) "Safeguarding academic and digital sovereignty: a model for action", *Expert Voices* (eua.eu), <https://eua.eu/resources/expert-voices/250:safeguarding-academic-and-digital-sovereignty-a-model-for-action.html>.
- <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/03/europe-digital-sovereignty/>
- [DORA: https://sfdora.org/](https://sfdora.org/), [Leiden Manifesto: http://www.leidenmanifesto.org/](http://www.leidenmanifesto.org/), [Hongkong principles: https://wcrif.org/guidance/hong-kong-principles](https://wcrif.org/guidance/hong-kong-principles).

APPENDIX A: OVERVIEW INFRASTRUCTURES IN USE

Infrastructure	Ownership and governance	Costs coverage	Long-term sustainability
Lund University			
CRIS system LUCRIS; based on Pure; with a repository for self-archiving connected	Corporate-based (Pure); joint governance between departments and faculties	LU management and/or difficulties	Annual and long-term plans for system management for each infrastructure: Swedish legal deposit, LOCKSS, SAFE PLN
Publication platform for journals and monographs; using OJS and OMP	open source (OJS,OMP); joint governance with departments and faculties	LU management and/or the faculties	
Lund University press; scholarly monographs publisher mainly in the humanities and social sciences			
University of Freiburg			
FreiDok plus – Institutional Repository that also serves as a university bibliography (in-house development based on Fedora)	Governed by the University library	Running costs covered by the budgets of the University library.	Permanent staff is in place Second copy is stored elsewhere. Additionally long-term archiving by the German National library.
Open Journal Systems & Open Encyclopedia System	Governed by the University library	Running costs covered by the budgets of the University library.	Permanent staff is in place
In the process of implementing multiple data publication platforms, such as FreiDATA (general purpose on software base InvenioRDM) and OMERO (biological microscopy data).	Governed by the University computer centre	Running costs covered by the budgets of the the University computer centre. Cost for development and implementation has been supported by research funding organisations and the State Ministry of science and research. Cost and operation models for financial participation of stakeholders with larger needs in development.	The open science platforms developed with time-limited project funds are difficult to transition to permanent services. There is a risk for the sustainability of such services.
Support for community driven efforts such as Galaxy platform for bioinformatics and contact.engineering for surface topography data			
Universiteit Leiden			
Scholarly repository; using islandora	University Leiden; the library governs the system administration, the ICT department service and application management	Paid by the library; pre-investment costs covered by the University and the University library jointly	Long-term archiving by the Royal Library
CRIS system using Converis		Paid by the library; faculties have their own CRIS managers who are paid by the faculty; pre-investment costs covered by the University and the University library jointly	

support for OAPEN, online library and publication platform for peer-reviewed OA academic books	OAPEN foundation; board of directors and advisory board of the foundation	Financial support by the University library and others; pre-investment co-funded by the EU and the 6 founders	Long-term archiving by the Royal Library
DataverseNL, jointly offered by 16 participating institutes and DANS using Dataverse software	DANS is managing the technical infrastructure; the participating institutes are responsible for managing the deposited data; all institutes participate in the advisory board	The costs are covered by the faculties that use the service; pre-investment cost covered by the University of Utrecht and DANS	
SURF Research drive, a cloud-based storage environment, hosted by SURF for securely storing and sharing research data	SURF; SURF is the collaborative organisation for IT in Dutch higher education and research.	The costs are covered by the faculty based on the actual cost of the service; pre-investment costs covered by SURF	
University of Amsterdam			
CRIS system; using Pure	Elsevier; governance through the consortium UvA-VU, UMCA, HvA with the library UvA/HvA as the leading contract order. Steering committee and active user group		
Repository UvA-DARE	University library; the library is in contact with the main stakeholders within the University: faculties (through the Pure managers and policy officers), the UvA executive staff and bureau communication		Publications are stored in the e-depot of the Royal Library
Data repository UvA/AUAS Figshare	Digital Science; the executive board has established central guidelines for research data management. This policy has been revised in January 2020. Faculties, research institutes and knowledge centres are working on formulating local policies and instructions. The UvA endorses the Netherlands code of conduct for academic integrity		Datasets are stored for a period of at least 10 years on the ISO certified server in Europe and provided with a DOI
Utrecht University			
Yoda for research data	Utrecht University; faculty data managers/stewards	Cost covered by faculties, IT department, University library and programme research IT	
GitHub for research software	Microsoft/GitHub; not governed	Free, administration by the IT department	
GitLab for research software	Self-hosted/Gitlab; science faculty IT department	Science faculty IT department	
Dataverse.nl for research data	DANS	Yearly fee paid by the University library and the IT department	

DSpace, a publication repository	Lyrasis, but local installation by Utrecht University; governed mainly by the international library community	University library	University library
KU Leuven	The executive board approves infrastructure roadmaps and long-term investments in infrastructures		Basic investment is a permanent element of the operating budget of the University. Explicit attention is given to the degree of sustainability in the procurement process
Leuven University press	KU Leuven	Setup as a business unit and largely dependent on external revenue streams	
Data repository RDR	KU Leuven; RDM steering committee presided by the Vice Rector for research policy	KU Leuven and the Flemish government	
Publication repository LIRIAS	KU Leuven; Research Coordination Office presided by the Vice Rector for research policy	KU Leuven	
Journals hosted on servers of particular faculty	KU Leuven;		
Research statistics tool (data partly from WoS)	KU Leuven; Research Coordination Office presided by the Vice Rector for research policy	KU Leuven and the Flemish government	
Sorbonne University			
HAL, national repository; the University manages its own portal	CCSD, Centre for direct scientific communication, a joint support and research unit of INRIA, CNRS and INRAE; governance at a national level with universities and other research organisations; there is an assembly of the 25 institutions that have a portal	IT department	
Recherche Data Gouv, the national French data repository to preserve, share and open the research data.	Ministry of Higher Education and Research, and operated by INRAE, the National research Institute in agronomy and environment; governance at a national level with universities and other research organisations	IT department	
University Paris-Saclay			
HAL, national repository; the University manages its own portal	CCSD, Centre for direct scientific communication, a joint support and research unit of INRIA, CNRS and INRAE; governance at a national level with universities and other research organisations; there is an assembly of the 25 institutions that have a portal	Annual fee of €18,000; 2.5 FTE local staff to operate the portal	Long-time archiving by CINES

Recherche Data Gouv, the national French data repository to preserve, share and open the research data. The University is currently working on the creation of an institutional space on this platform.	Ministry of Higher Education and Research, and operated by INRAE, the National research Institute in agronomy and environment; governance at a national level with universities and other research organisations	No subscription fee: estimated 1 FTE local staff to manage the institutional space	Still in process, possibly also by CINES
The University develops a mesocentre designed to provide researchers with major technical platforms for computing and data processing.	Paris-Saclay Mésocentre is a local infrastructure, operated by the University, its interconnect several existing structures at the University level and progressively gathers and mutualizes computer and storage resources formally disseminated in the laboratories: a board of experts representing the various substructures in the University and ultimately by the University research and innovation Council	Mixed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - part of the resources has been financed by national and regional grants - heavy users are requested to pay - University takes care of electricity and ancillary services - The mesocentre has been designed by high energy physicist and by researchers in fluid mechanics. 	
University of Strasbourg			Permanent staff is in place for some infrastructures
Open access repository for publications (Islandora 7)	Open source; local infrastructure is owned by the University; local committees such as the open science steering committee and the digital project steering committee	University of Strasbourg	
Data repository: institutional collection on Recherche Data Gouv	Owned by national services or institutions; national governance	National institutions	
Publication platforms Presses Universitaires de Strasbourg (with Open Edition, using LODEL platform)	Owned by national services or institutions; national governance	National institutions	
University of Zurich			No clear mechanisms in place
ZORA local repository for publications, using open-source software Eprints	University of Zurich; governance not clearly stated; basic principles discussed with the executive board	By the library budget	
HOPE publishing platform, using open-source software OJS	University of Zurich; governance not clearly stated; basic principles discussed with the executive board	By the library budget, initially co-founded by a national funding scheme	
National data platform SWISSUbase; proprietary software developed by FORS, the Swedish centre of expertise in the social sciences	A legal entity called 'simple partnership'; governance by this legal entity	By temporary dedicated funds (long-term funding not yet solved); initially co-founded by a national funding scheme	
Université de Genève			

UNIGE - Publication repository; based on Fedora	University of Geneva; internal steering committees	Covered by the regular budget of the University	
Yareta - data repository; based on DLCM technology	University of Geneva; internal steering committees	Mixed model with a starting grant from Geneva state to cover free services and premium offers	Actual funding from the Swiss National Science Foundation, the rest from the University of other grants, as well as asking fees to users for depositing data (based on volume)
Open access journal hosting platform; using OJS	University of Geneva; internal steering committees	Covered by the regular budget of the University	
Universitat de Barcelona			
Institutional repository for any contents; based on DSpace	University of Barcelona; managing staff covered by the library, technical staff and service covered by IT department		
Institutional portal for scientific journal; OJS system	University of Barcelona; managing staff covered by the library, technical staff and service covered by IT department		
Repository for research data; based on data verse; the University participates as a partner in a common infrastructure	CSUC - the Catalan Consortium for University services; managing staff covered by the library, technical staff and service covered by IT department		
University of Helsinki			
The national library of Finland is a cultural heritage organisation and the separate unity of the University of Helsinki. The NLF maintains several national infrastructures such as: National line sensing (FinELib); the below-mentioned institutional repository service, a national portal for the GLAM sector and digitised materials for research et cetera.			
Digital repository; based on DSpace	The National library of Finland offers this service to is about 50 research and/or public organisations; the library owns the infrastructure;, the content is owned by the contributing organisations; the strategic choice has been made to use open-source solutions where appropriate; there is a steering structure for national services..	Participating organisations cover the cost; the CSC provides long-term preservation services.	
CRIS system; using Pure			
Various data repository infrastructures	University IT centre		

Platform for open journal publishing; based on OJS	The library		
National services for research data management and storage			
Trinity College Dublin			
In-house developed CRIS system; developed in APEX (Oracle)	University/Dean of research; governance is provided by the library and information policy community, a subcommittee of the University board	External project funding and research overheads covers support staff and content, alongside central college funds; pre-investment for designing, setting up and lounging this infrastructures comes from the central college funding of staff in the relevant areas and/or external project funding	
Institutional repository (linked to the CRIS system); based on DSpace	University/Dean of research (the metadata and the content are owned by the individual researchers, who can give permission for it to be publicly displayed, shared with external systems et cetera); governance is provided by the library and information policy community, a subcommittee of the University board	External project funding and research overheads covers support staff and content, alongside central college funds; pre-investment for designing, setting up and lounging this infrastructures comes from the central college funding of staff in the relevant areas and/or external project funding	
Journal publication platform; based on OJS			
Omeka for arts and humanities digital exhibitions			
Centralised infrastructure for research data			
University of Milan			
CRIS system – a national system hosted by CINECA (technological part of the Italian universities) and based on DSpace	National and governed by the Italian universities	The Italian universities	
Institutional data repository (a Dataverse instance)			
OA Diamond University Press based on OJS and OMP [57 journals and books and series]	Governed by the editorial boards and managed by the university	The University of Milan	
University of Edinburgh			
Pure acts as a CRIS and publications repository; maintained by the Library Research support, hosted by Elsevier	The University of Edinburgh; academic-led steering groups and senior leadership team of information services. Services use ITIL-based service management framework, including service owners and service operations managers	In the past, JICS projects led to development of infrastructure. Currently internal investment (e.g., Digital Research Services programme and core funding	Policies, investment in digital preservation (e.g., CoreTrustSeal certification for DataShare); core funding plus development funding.
Edinburgh Research Archive acts as a repository for theses and other digital objects (DSpace); maintained and hosted by Digital Library			
Edinburgh DataShare, institutional open access data repository institutional open access data repository (DSpace); Maintained and hosted by Digital Library			

DataVault, institutional long time data retention solution; hardware hosted by IT infrastructure, software by Digital Library			
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APPENDIX B: OVERVIEW STAKEHOLDERS IN TASKS

Workflow management	Dissemination and discovery	Authentication, authorisation, and access	Research data management (screening, FAIR archiving)	Next generation metrics	Long-term preservation	
Support services for open science (in the Quality Assurance unit)	Support services for open science	Support services for open science	Support services for open science	Support services for open science	Support services for open science and ICT	Milan
University library, ITS	University library	University library	University library	Open science programme; University library	University library	Utrecht
University library; University computer centre	University library; University computer centre	University library; University computer centre central administration	University library; University computer centre researchers	Researchers University library; University computer centre	University library; University computer centre Researchers	Freiburg
Library IT services	Library	IT services	depending on the disciplines for FAIR archiving: the library		Library	Zurich: we do foresee the need of access committee for datasets that have been deposited in the closed contract, if authors can't be contacted anymore or in cases of potential deletion of published data
Output (not data): the library Data: the faculty	Output (not data): the library Data: service provider	Output (not data): the library with ICT Data: service provider	Data: data steward of the faculty, individual researchers	Central policymakers and the coordinator 'reward and recognition'	Output (not data): the library and the Royal Library Data: service provider	Leiden
Library (including LIBIS as technical partner of the repositories), research coordination	Library (including LIBIS as technical partner of the repositories), research coordination	Library (including LIBIS as technical partner of the repositories), research coordination office, ICTS,	Researchers ICTS Library (including LIBIS as technical partner of the repositories)	Research coordination office	Library (including LIBIS as technical partner of the repositories) ICTS for storage LUP for its own titles	Leuven

office, LUP for its own titles	office, LUP for its own titles	LUP for its own titles				
Repositories: library Publishing platforms: editorial teams	Repositories: library Publishing platforms: editorial teams	Repositories: library and IT services	Researchers and support services in the lap	Nobody	IT services and national institutions (CINES)	Strasbourg
HAL platform offers a standard workflow; the researcher makes the deposit; the librarians are in charge of the technical validation	The research at the time of his deposit can choose between several dissemination options	Researchers	On our recherche.data.gouv institutional space, the data librarians will make the deposits in connection with the research teams	Basic new generation metrics available on HAL (number of retweets)	Handled by the repository HAL through CINES	Paris Saclay
Curation by HAL (CCSD)	HAL (CCSD)	HAL (CCSD)			CINES	Sorbonne University
Faculty, library, and automated service	Library and alternated service	Faculty, library, and automated service	Faculty, library	Faculty, library	Library, service provider	University of Amsterdam
Library	Library	library and IT	library, researchers	Nobody	IT	Barcelona
Libraries and research support services are responsible for managing the workflow in the CRIS system editor's managed workflow in OJS and OMP	University communication Department, research services, library	Depends on the system. Responsibilities are described in the system management plans	A group that addresses RDM issues have been formed and includes library staff from different faculties at the University	University management, national policies, research board of the University	IT services and University archives. Long-term preservation is sometimes managed by faculties. In some cases, commercial solutions are being used. The University is decentralised and lacks a central plan regarding long-term preservation	Lund
Library	Library	IT department	Library	Library and IT departments	Library	University of Edinburgh
-	-	IT division	IT division and library	-	IT division and library	Geneva